

ETHNOBOTANICAL STUDY OF WILD EDIBLE PLANTS USED BY TRIBALS OF DHAR DISTRICT, MADHYA PRADESH, INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The paper deals with the information are based on an ethnobotanical study of wild edible plants used by Tribals of Dhar district, Madhya Pradesh, India, during 2024-2026. The first-hand information on 68 plant species belonging to 52 genera and 40 families were collected and identified. The tribals living in remote forest areas with respected to food plants showed that tribals depend much upon forest products for their eaten a variety of wild edible plants. In the all plant species such utilized of wild edible plants, viz. *Aegle marmelos* (L.) Correa, *Amaranthus spinosus* L., *Amorphophalus paeniifolius* (Dennst.) Nicolson, *Anogeissus latifolia* Wall, *Argyrea nervosa* (Burm f.)Boj, *Bauhinia variegata* L., *Borassus flabellifer* L., *Buchanania lanzan* Spreng, *Butea monosperma*, Lamk, *Carissa spinarum* L., *Cassia fistula* Linn., *Cordia dichotoma* GForst., *Diospyros melanoxylon* Roxb., *Ensete superbum*(Roxb.) Cheesman, *Madhucalongifoliavar .latifolia*(Roxb.)A Chev, *Senna tora* (L.) Roxb. etc. were observed.

KEYWORDS: Dhar district, Ethnobotanical study, forest areas, Tribals, Wild edible plants.

INTRODUCTION

Dhar district is situated in the southwestern part of Madhya Pradesh, India. The study area lies between 22° 00 to 23° 10 Northern latitude and 74° 28 to 75° 42 Eastern longitude. Its area is about 8153 Sq. Km. and geographical area of 1214.8 Sq.km. Its population is 2184672 (Census 2011). the tribal people constitute over 83.93 percent of the population. The chief tribes in the district are Bheel, Bhilala, Barela and Pateliya. The Bheel people move around the forest for their day today requirements, cultural activities and performing rituals. These tribal live close to the forest and largely dependent on the wild biological resources for their livelihood. They utilize wide variety of plant for their basic needs such as food, fodder, fiber, wood, medicine, gum, tannin, resin, dye and shelter. Literature survey of ethnobotanical work was done (Jain 2004, Alawa *et al.* 2012; Alawa *et al.* 2016, Alawa 2021; Jadhav 2010; Jain *et al.* 2010, Kalakoti *et al.*, Maheshwari *et al.* 1986, Singh *et al.* 2001, Satya *et al.* 2010, Wagh *et al.* 2010). Therefore study has been undertaken to record

ethnobotanical from different tribal communities of these study areas.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present paper communication given results of ethnobotanical study of wild edible plants used by Tribals of Dhar district, Madhya Pradesh, India. Ethnobotanical field work was carried out during 2024-2026, covering almost all seasons. Interviews were taken to gather the information's on plants used for other than wild edible plants purposes are also given. Information was obtained through field interviews. The plant specimens were collected, identified with the help of Herbarium and Floras (Mudgal *et al.*, 1997; Verma *et al.*, 1993; Jain, 1991). Herbarium following standard method (Jain and Rao, 1977). Deposited in the herbarium of the Department of Botany PMB Gujarati Science College, Indore (M.P.). Some of the wild edible plants were photographed documented (Fig. 1-6). Plants were enumerated alphabetically according to their scientific

name, family, local name, parts used, and mode of preparation (Table-1).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present study 68 plant species belonging to 52 genera and 40 families are discussed above which are used. Wild edible plants are prepared from leaves, flowers, fruits, rhizome, young shoots on the basis of the parts used. Ripe fruits of 17 species, leaves of 15 species, flowers buds of 4 and young flowers of 4 species, fruits of 10 species and young shoots, tubers,

stem bark, rhizome of 2 specie each, gum and inflorescence of 1 species each are used as wild edible plants. Wild edible plants are regularly eaten by tribals, either cooked or as separate preparation. Some of this forest produce is consumed as it is collected in the forest. Such is the case with all the wild edible plants. It is seen that all parts are of the plants eaten are used as wild edible plants. Most of the tribals live in remote hilly areas.

Fig.1 *Cassia fistula* L.

Fig.2 *Butea monosperma* Lamk.

Fig.3 *Ensete superbum* (Roxb.)Chees.

Fig.4 *Drimia indica* (Roxb.) Jess

Fig.5 *Amorphophalus paeoniifolius* (Den.) Nico.

Fig.6 *Diospyros melanoxylon* Roxb.

Fig. (1-6) Wild edible plants used by tribals of Dhar district (M.P.)

Table-1: Wild edible plants used by tribals of Dhar district (M.P.)

S.No.	Botanical name	Family	Vernacular Name	Habit	Plan parts and mode of preparation
1.	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.)Correa	Rutaceae	Bel	Tree	Ripen fruits are as raw or shake are consumed
2.	<i>Alangi umsalviifolium</i> (L.f.)Wangerin	Cornaceae	Ankol	Tree	Fruit pulp edible
3.	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	Katili Chaurai	Herb	Leaves and young twigs are used as vegetable
4.	<i>Amaranthus viridis</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	Chaurai	Herb	Seeds are used as grains during scarcity of food.
5.	<i>Amorphophalus paeoniifolius</i> (Dennst.) Nicolson	Araceae	Jangli suran	Herb	Corm boiled and eaten .boiled and eaten.
6.	<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	Annonaceae	Sitaphal	Tree	Ripe Fruits are edible and eaten
7.	<i>Anogeissus latifolia</i> Wall	Combretaceae	Dhawada	Tree	Stem bark and gum
8.	<i>Argyreia nervosa</i> (Burm f.)Boj	Convolvulaceae	Phang-vela	Climber	Leaves are used as green vegetable.
9.	<i>Avena sativa</i> Linn.	Poaceae	Jai /Oat	Shrub	Seeds are consumed.
10.	<i>Basella alba</i> L.	Basellaceae	Poi sag	Climber	Leaves and stem are used as vegetable.
11.	<i>Bauhinia variegata</i> L.	Fabaceae	Kachnar	Tree	Floral buds

12.	<i>Bombax ceiba</i> L.	Bombacaceae	Semal	Tree	Young flowers & stem are consumed during scarcity of food. Seeds edible.
13.	<i>Borassus flabellifer</i> L.	Arecaceae	Tad	Tree	Fleshy endocarp is eaten
14.	<i>Buchanania lanzan</i> Spreng.	Anacardiaceae	Char	Climber	Fruits and seeds are consumed.
15.	<i>Buchananiacochinchinensis</i> (Lour)M.R.Almeida	Anacardiaceae	Chironji/ Achar	Tree	Seeds are consumed.
16.	<i>Butea monosperma</i> , Lamk.	Fabaceae	Palas	Tree	Young Floral buds
17.	<i>Careya arborea</i> Roxb.	Lecythidaceae	Kumbhi	Tree	Leaves are used as vegetable. Fruits are eaten raw.
18.	<i>Carissa spinarum</i> L.	Apocynaceae	Karonda	Shrub	Ripe fruits are eaten raw. Unripe fruits are used as vegetable.
19.	<i>Cassia fistula</i> Linn	Caesalpiniaceae	Amaltas	Tree	Leaves and young floral buds
20.	<i>Catunaregam spinosa</i> (Thunb.) Tirveng	Rubiaceae	Mainphal	Tree	Ripe fruits are eaten after cooking.
21.	<i>Ceropegia bulbosa</i> Roxb.	Asclepiadaceae	Khadula	Herb	Leaves are eaten as vegetable. Bulbs are boiled and eaten.
22.	<i>Cheilocostus speciosus</i> (Koenig) J E Smith	Zingiberaceae	Keukand	Herb	Tubers are washed, cooked and eaten as vegetables.
23.	<i>Chenopodium album</i> Linn.	Chenopodiaceae	Bathua	Herb	Tender shoots
24.	<i>Coccinia grandis</i> (L.)Voight	Cucurbitaceae	Tundru/ Berikand	Climber	Green fruits are consumed as vegetable.
25.	<i>Coccinia indica</i> W.& A.	Cucurbitaceae	Kundru	Climber	Unripe fruits as vegetable.
26.	<i>Cordia dichotoma</i> GForst.	Boraginaceae	Gondi	Tree	Young inflorescence and floral buds are consumed.
27.	<i>Cordia macleodii</i> Hook.f ex Thompson	Boraginaceae	Gondi	Tree	Flowers are edible
28.	<i>Cyperus esculent</i> Linn	Cyperaceae	Gondila	Herb	Rhizome
29.	<i>Dendrocalamus strictus</i> (Roxb. Nees	Poaceae	Baans	Tree	Tender shoots are edible and consumed as food.
30.	<i>Dioscorea hispida</i> Dennst.	Discoreaceae	Jangli kand	climber	Tubers are boiled, peeled off and eaten.
31.	<i>Diospyros melanoxylon</i> Roxb.	Ebenaceae	Temru	Tree	Ripe fruit of temru is eaten.
32.	<i>Drimia indica</i> (Roxb.)Jessop	Asparagaceae	Jangli kanda	Herb	Leaves are used as vegetable.
33.	<i>Ensete superbum</i> (Roxb.) Cheesman	Musaceae	Jangli kela	Shrub	Rhizomes boiled and eaten. Unripe fruits are used as vegetables.
34.	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> , Linn	Moraceae	Bad/Bar	Tree	Ripe fruits
35.	<i>Ficus racemosa</i> , Linn.	Moraceae	Gular	Tree	Unripe fruits as vegetable
36.	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> , Linn.	Moraceae	Peepal	Tree	Ripe fruits
37.	<i>Ficus lacor</i> Buch-Ham	Moraceae	Pipar	Tree	Fruits are edible
38.	<i>Grewia subaequalis</i> Baill.	Malvaceae	Phalsa	Tree	Fruits are edible.
39.	<i>Grewia tilifolia</i> Vahl.	Malvaceae	Dhaman	Tree	Fruits are edible
40.	<i>Ipomoea aquatica</i> Forssk.	Convolvulaceae		Climber	Young twigs and leaves are used as vegetable
41.	<i>Macratamia uniflorum</i> (Lam.)V erdc.	Fabaceae	Kulthi	Herb	Seeds are consumed as food
42.	<i>Madhucal longifolia</i> var <i>.latifolia</i> (Roxb.)A Chev	Sapotaceae	Mahua	Tree	Fleshy petals are eaten.
43.	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Anacardiaceae	Aam	Tree	Ripe fruits are eaten. Pickles are prepared from unripe green fruits.
44.	<i>Manilkara hexandra</i> (Roxb.) Dubard	Sapotaceae	Khirmi	Tree	Ripe fruits are eaten.
45.	<i>Momordica dioica</i> Roxb.ex Willd.	Cucurbitaceae	Katele	Climber	Young green unripe fruits are used as green vegetable.
46.	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	Moringaceae	Surjjana	Tree	Young leaves and Green fruits

					are consumed as vegetable. Flowers are also eaten.
47.	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L.	Oxalidaceae	KhattiBhaji	Herb	Leaves are used as vegetable during scarcity of food.
48.	<i>Phoenix sylvestris</i> (L.)Roxb.	Arecaceae	Khajur	Tree	Ripe fruits are eaten raw
49.	<i>Phyllanthusemblica</i> L.	Phyllanthaceae	Amla	Tree	Ripe fruits are directly eaten.
50.	<i>Pithecellobiumdulce</i> (Roxb.)B enth.	Fabaceae	Vilayti babul	Tree	Ripe fruits are eaten.
51.	<i>Portulacaquadrifida</i> L.	Portulacaceae	Bhaji	Herb	Young leaves are consumed as vegetable.
52.	<i>Pueraria tuberosa</i> , Linn	Fabaceae	Bidarikand	Climber	Young tuber
53.	<i>Riveahypocrateriformis</i> Choisy	Convolvulaceae	Pan bel	Climber	Leaves are used as vegetable
54.	<i>Schleichera oleosa</i> , Oken	Sapindaceae	Kusum	Tree	Fresh fruits
55.	<i>Semecarpus anacardium</i> ,Linn	Anacardiaceae	Bhelma	Tree	Fruits
56.	<i>Senna tora</i> (L.)Roxb.	Fabaceae	Povadiya	Herb	Young leaves are used as vegetable.
57.	<i>Sesbania grandiflora</i> (L.)Poir	Fabaceae		Tree	Flowers are fried and eaten.
58.	<i>Shorea robusta</i> , Gaertn	Dipterocarpaceae	Salai/sal	Tree	Leaves and Seeds
59.	<i>Solanum nigrum</i> L.	Solanaceae	Makoi	Herb	Unripe fruits were used as green vegetables.
60.	<i>Solanumxanthocarpum</i> Schrad& J.C Wendle.	Solanaceae	Bhatkateiya	Herb	Young green fruits are consumed as green vegetable.
61.	<i>Spondiaspinnata</i> (L.F.)Kurz.	Anacardiaceae	Amadi	Tree	Fruits are edible.
62.	<i>Syzigiumcumini</i> Keels	Myrtaceae	Jamun	Tree	Fruits are edible.
63.	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	Fabaceae	Imli	Tree	Ripe pods are edible Unripe fruits are also eaten.
64.	<i>Terminaliabellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.	Combretaceae	Baheda	Tree	Seeds are consumed.
65.	<i>Trapanatans</i> L.	Lythraceae	Singhada	Herb	Seeds are roasted and eaten
66.	<i>Trianthemaportulacastrum</i> L.	Aizoaceae	Bhaji	Herb	Leaves are used as vegetables
67.	<i>Ziziphusjuzuba</i> Mill	Rhamnaceae	Ber	Tree	Ripe Fruits are eaten.
68.	<i>Ziziphus xylopyrus</i> (Retz.) Willd.	Rhamnaceae	Khatti ber	Tree	Ripe Fruits are eaten.

CONCLUSION

Ethnobotanical study of wild edible plants used by Tribals of Dhar district, Madhya Pradesh, India. In the present study 68 plant species belonging to 52 genera and 40 families are discussed above which are used. Wild edible plants are prepared from Ripe fruits, leaves, flowers, fruits, rhizome, young shoots on the basis of the parts used. Wild edible plants are regularly eaten by tribal people.

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